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7 **On the characterization and rank assignment criteria for the**
8 **anaerobic fungi (Neocallimastigomycota)**

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Abstract

Within a specific lineage, establishing a solid taxonomic framework is crucial for enabling discovery and documentation efforts. This ensures effective communication between scientists as well as reproducibility of results between laboratories, and facilitates the exchange and preservation of biological material. Such framework can only be achieved by establishing clear criteria for taxa characterization and rank assignment. Within the anaerobic fungi (Phylum Neocallimastigomycota), the need for such criteria is especially vital. Difficulties associated with their isolation, maintenance, and long-term storage often result in limited availability and loss of previously described taxa. To this end, we provide here a list of morphological, microscopic, phylogenetic, and phenotypic criteria for assessment and documentation when characterizing newly obtained Neocallimastigomycota isolates. We also recommend a polyphasic rank-assignment scheme for novel genus, species, and strain level designations for newly obtained Neocallimastigomycota isolates.

58 Members of the kingdom fungi colonize a wide range of terrestrial, aquatic, marine, animal- and
59 plant-associated ecosystems; and collectively display a great capacity for growth and survival
60 under a wide range of environmental conditions [1]. This remarkable niche adaptation ability is
61 reflected in the high level of morphotypic, microscopic, phenotypic, and genomic traits exhibited
62 by members of the kingdom. Fungal taxonomists investigate the relationships between and
63 within fungal lineages by identifying, assessing, and comparing such traits across taxa. The
64 broad field of fungal taxonomy encompasses nomenclature (assigning names and establishing
65 procedures for naming), characterization (defining and utilizing a set of experimental procedures
66 to document informative traits allowing discrimination between taxa), and classification
67 (establishing a framework for assigning taxa into taxonomic ranks, and utilizing such framework
68 for assigning ranks to newly isolated strains). Fungal nomenclature is governed by the
69 International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (ICNafp; the *Code* for short).
70 The *Code* [2] sets formal requirements for nomenclature of novel taxa, including registration of
71 nomenclature novelties in recognized repositories (MycoBank or Index Fungorum), type
72 designation, type material deposition in appropriate repositories, and guidelines for publication
73 of a valid name and ensuring its legitimacy. Criteria for characterization and classification are
74 set-forth by the International Committee of Taxonomy of Fungi (ICTF). The recent manuscript
75 by Aime et al. [3] elaborates on the best practices for ensuring availability of descriptive data and
76 preventing publication of taxonomically superfluous names. However, unlike rules of
77 nomenclature that are applicable to all the Mycota, criteria for characterization and
78 classification/rank assignment can differ greatly between fungal lineages. As such, lineage-
79 specific guidelines for characterization and classification should be developed and formulated by
80 the relevant scientific community [3].

81 The anaerobic fungi (Phylum Neocallimastigomycota) inhabit the alimentary tract of
82 herbivores, and display multiple adaptive strategies that enable them to survive and thrive in this
83 permanently anoxic, prokaryote-dominated ecosystem. Multiple novel anaerobic fungal genera
84 [4-10], and species [11-13] have recently been described. In spite of such progress, criteria for
85 characterization and rank assignment for novel isolates in the Neocallimastigomycota have not
86 been formulated, although discussions on the relative importance of specific traits as part of rank
87 assignment justifications in some prior taxa description manuscripts [4, 7, 14] have been
88 proposed. Therefore, the purpose of this manuscript is twofold. Firstly to provide a list of
89 morphological, microscopic, phylogenetic, and phenotypic criteria that should be assessed and
90 documented when characterizing newly obtained Neocallimastigomycota isolates. Secondly, to
91 suggest a rank assignment scheme for accommodating newly obtained Neocallimastigomycota
92 isolates. This is especially important for the anaerobic gut fungi, due to difficulties associated
93 with their isolation, maintenance and long-term storage.

94 Prior to undertaking detailed characterization efforts, ensuring the purity of isolates
95 obtained is vital. Anaerobic fungi could be co-isolated or contaminated by bacteria and
96 methanogenic Archaea during the isolation and maintenance process. Alternatively, mixed
97 cultures of anaerobic gut fungi could be obtained during the isolation process. To ensure purity,
98 isolates should be derived from a single colony rather than by dilution to extinction procedures,
99 and multiple rounds of dilution, rolling tubes and colony picking of the culture is recommended.
100 Utilization of various antibiotic cocktails to guard against bacterial contamination is commonly
101 employed, and occurrence of contamination is assessed by microscopic observation.
102 Amplification and direct sequencing of genes known to exhibit minimal strain variability could

103 be undertaken, with the quality of obtained sequencing data used as an additional confirmation of
104 the purity of the sample.

105 **Proposed criteria for Neocallimastigomycota characterization.**

106 A list of morphotypic, microscopic, phenotypic, and phylogenetic criteria recommended for
107 describing novel Neocallimastigomycota isolates is provided in Table 1. The proposed criteria
108 were formulated through in-depth discussions within the community of Neocallimastigomycota
109 taxonomists, as well as by assessing arguments presented in prior taxa description papers [4-7,
110 14] and reviews [15] during the last four decades. The criteria are meant to be thorough and
111 detailed in order to enable consistent and information-grounded assessments of novelty, and to
112 preserve knowledge for future comparative purposes. However, they are not meant to be onerous
113 to the point of discouraging characterization efforts or to dictate a specific formatting over
114 another (e.g. full-length manuscripts over fungal diversity notes). The criteria are also not
115 intended to constrain characterization efforts; and reporting additional traits should certainly be
116 encouraged (for example, documenting unique previously unreported microscopic structures,
117 unique growth phenotypes, information on gene copy numbers for various loci, and levels of
118 enzymatic activities).

119 The utilization of multi-locus based phylogeny [16], whole genome phylogenomic
120 analysis [17], genome-wide synteny [18], and amino acid identity estimates [19] in
121 Neocallimastigomycota taxonomy could provide extremely valuable additional information and
122 thresholds for circumscribing ranks within the lineage. Such efforts for anaerobic fungi,
123 however, have lagged behind other major fungal lineages. This is a reflection of the lack of
124 adequate genome/transcriptome coverage for all representative genera, as well as the loss of
125 multiple historic strains. However, while the value and insights provided by comparative –omics

126 approaches are undisputed, undertaking of such efforts is not proposed as a requirement for the
127 taxa description process in the *Neocallimastigomycota*.

128 Finally, it is important to note that, while in the prokaryotic world, the International
129 Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes (ICSP) would set forth subcommittees to enact
130 minimal and recommended standards for description of novel genera and species; no such
131 requirements are set forth for by the ICTF for Fungi. As such, the criteria proposed here are
132 meant to establish an agreement in the community regarding the Neocallimastigomycota and to
133 guide the expectations of authors, reviewers and editors. Details and illustrations of the listed
134 morphotypic and microscopic features have been provided in prior reviews [15, 20]. The relative
135 importance of various criteria are highlighted in Table 1.

136 **Species hypothesis and rank assignment in the Neocallimastigomycota.**

137 What criteria govern the accommodation of an anaerobic fungal isolate into a specific rank, and
138 how could such boundaries be circumscribed? Analysis of prior taxa description papers
139 demonstrates wide variations in arguments set forth for rank assignments. Many earlier studies
140 were “splitters”, proposing a new species designation based on minor criteria, some of which
141 could be a function of inter-laboratory variability and/or media composition (e.g. *Caecomyces*
142 *communis* and *C. equi* [21], *Piromyces communis* and *P. dumbonicus* [22], *Neocallimastix*
143 *frontalis* and *N. hurleyensis* [23]), see references [15] and [29] for additional details. New
144 species have also been proposed based on the identification of specific microscopic trait(s), but
145 such traits could have been overlooked in taxa description manuscripts of closest relatives. More
146 recent studies have proposed new species for morphologically identical strains solely based on
147 sequence divergence values (e.g. *P. irregularis* [11]). On the other hand, some studies have been
148 extremely conservative in rank assignment, proposing a new species in spite of clear differences

149 justifying proposition of a new genus e.g. (e.g. *Neocallimastix joyonii* [24]). Furthermore, earlier
150 studies relied solely on microscopic data, while newer taxa description manuscripts reported both
151 microscopic as well as molecular data (e.g. ITS1, D1/D2 loci). Recent comparative studies have
152 attempted to utilize a broader whole genome phylogenomic approach for taxa delineation [17].
153 However, as stated above, these efforts, while extremely promising, require the broad availability
154 of genomic and transcriptomic data. Further, preliminary efforts have suggested that tree
155 topologies recovered by whole genome phylogenomic analysis are often accurately reflected by
156 those recovered by D1/D2 LSU phylogenetic analysis. As such, generation and assessment of
157 whole genome or transcriptome –omics data is not seen as absolutely required when formulating
158 rank assignment decisions for new isolates within the Neocallimastigomycota.

159 Due to the lack of consistency in rank assignment approaches highlighted above, we
160 propose guidelines for combining microscopic features and phylogenetic analysis for rank
161 assignment decisions in the Neocallimastigomycota. Broadly, the scheme is guided by the
162 following principles:

- 163 • Zoospore flagellation pattern (monoflagellated or polyflagellated), thallus developmental
164 pattern (monocentric or polycentric, determined by 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) or
165 Bisbenzimidazole staining of live cultures and visualization using a fluorescence microscope), and
166 rhizoidal growth pattern (filamentous or bulbous) are genus-defining criteria in the
167 Neocallimastigomycota. All species within a genus should display the same phenotype with
168 regards to these three criteria.
- 169 • Novel genera and species designations require clear documentation of phylogenetic novelty in
170 both ITS1 and D1/D2 LSU loci at specific thresholds, as well as documenting clear and stable
171 differences in macroscopic and/or microscopic features from the nearest described taxa.

172 • Subspecies and *conferre* (*cf.*) strain designations should be used for naming isolates that do
173 not clear the proposed thresholds for genus and species novelty.

174 Specifically, we propose that a novel genus designation should be conferred on new isolates
175 forming a monophyletic clade that is distinct from all previously described genera in D1/D2 LSU
176 and ITS1 phylogenetic trees with adequate statistical support (e.g. >70% bootstrap, >95%
177 posterior probability) and exhibiting unambiguous morphological differences to their closest
178 phylogenetic relatives in one or more of the three cardinal criteria of spore flagellation, thallus
179 developmental, and rhizoidal growth patterns. Detection of a difference in such criteria would
180 justify proposing a new genus, regardless of percentage sequence divergence estimates to its
181 closest cultured and described relative. In cases in which no such differences are observed; a new
182 genus should only be proposed based on exhibiting a high level of sequence divergence in
183 D1/D2 LSU and ITS1 loci that justifies accommodation as a new genus rather than a species.

184 Sequence divergence values are clearly a function of the region amplified, alignment methods
185 (pairwise versus multiple sequence alignments), and settings employed (e.g. gap opening and
186 gap extension penalties). A minimum D1/D2 LSU sequence divergence threshold of 3% from the
187 closest relative (calculated using BLASTn with the default parameters of gap existence cost, 5;
188 gap extension cost, 2; match score, 2; mismatch score, -3) against cultured, validly described
189 taxa (as defined by *the Code* as stated above, see reference [20]
190 <https://zenodo.org/record/5772823#.YbPCTh0krIG> for a recent list) is proposed for genus level
191 delineation. Utilizing this threshold value with existing genera yielded groupings consistent with
192 the current ones with two exceptions: the genus *Piromyces* where the intra-genus sequence
193 divergence cutoff of the D1/D2-LSU region ranges between 0% and 5.7%, and the
194 *Anaeromyces-Liebetanzomyces-Capellomyces-Oontomyces* clade where the inter-genus sequence

195 divergence ranges between 1.8% and 2.5%. However, within this clade, the propositions of
196 different genera have been justified based on a clear difference in thallus developmental patterns
197 (polycentric in *Anaeromyces* versus monocentric in all other genera), a criterion that justifies
198 proposing a new genus regardless of sequence divergence estimates, as stated earlier. Similarly, a
199 minimum ITS1 sequence divergence threshold of 5% from the closest relative (calculated using
200 BLASTn with the default parameters outlined above) against cultured, validly described taxa is
201 proposed for genus level delineation. This threshold value is based on similar assessments of
202 inter-genus sequence divergence estimates [25, 26], and has subsequently been utilized in
203 culture-independent diversity surveys [27, 28].

204 We propose that a novel species designation within an existing genus should be used to
205 accommodate isolate(s) forming a monophyletic branch that is distinct from all other species
206 within the genus in both D1/D2 LSU and ITS1 phylogenetic trees. Multiple ITS1 and D1/D2
207 LSU sequences from strain(s), especially the type strain, should be examined (Table 1). There
208 could potentially be occasional overlaps between one or more ITS1 sequences from a novel
209 species and those from an existing species within the same genus due to the wide within-strain
210 ITS1 sequence divergence [29]. However, encountering overlaps in D1/D2 LSU rRNA sequence
211 trees should preclude proposing a novel species.

212 Several factors should be taken into consideration when proposing minimum D1/D2 LSU
213 or ITS1 sequence divergence thresholds for novel species assignment. Only seven out of the
214 twenty currently described genera have more than one species. Within these genera, the majority
215 of prior rank assignment decisions were primarily based on microscopic differences. Within
216 genera with multiple species for which sequence information is available, D1/D2 LSU sequence
217 divergence ranged between 1.8% (i.e. for *Capellomyces foraminis* versus *C. elongis*, and

218 *Orpinomyces joyonii* versus *O. intercalaris*), and 2.2% (i.e. for *Neocallimastix frontalis* versus *N.*
219 *cameroonii*, and *Anaeromyces mucronatus* versus *A. contortus*). As such, a threshold value of
220 2% is proposed, and such value has been utilized for species-level operational taxonomic unit
221 (OTU) designation in culture-independent surveys [29]. Similarly, an ITS1 sequence divergence
222 estimate of 2% is proposed as a general guide for species-level assignments, while taking into
223 account within-strain sequence divergence, a phenomenon that could result in a range of values
224 when utilizing various copies of the ITS1 locus. This value has also been suggested in [25] and
225 utilized for species-level OTU designation in subsequent diversity surveys [27, 28].

226 In addition, assessment of all traits described in Table 1, and comparison to all other
227 members of the genus should be undertaken. Distinct differences in one or more stable
228 morphological feature(s) are commonly observed between new and existing species within the
229 same genus, e.g. the formation of intercalary sporangia in *Orpinomyces intercalaris*
230 differentiates it from *O. joyonii*. Reporting such characteristics represents a very important
231 resource to enhance knowledge of the genus overall characteristics and capabilities.

232 We propose that a subspecies designation should be utilized to describe strains that show
233 low sequence divergence when compared to previously reported and validly published
234 Neocallimastigomycota species, and/or exhibit minor differences in microscopic and/or
235 phenotypic traits, e.g. substrate utilization patterns, fermentation products, growth rate, size and
236 organization of specific microscopic structures. Finally, strains exhibiting exact morphological,
237 microscopic, phylogenetic, and phenotypic criteria should be designated as *cf.* strains for existing
238 species [20].

239 The requirements highlighted above are mostly concerned with procedures for validly
240 describing and naming novel isolates, as well as for their assignment to a specific rank within the

241 Neocallimastigomycota. Such procedures, however, should not impede progress in wider aspects
242 of Neocallimastigomycota biology. Indeed, the use of alphanumeric designations to identify
243 strains has been a long-standing and widely accepted approach in the fields of biotechnology
244 [30-33], biochemistry [34-36], and cell biology [37, 38], and beyond.

245 Finally, it is important to note that the proposed criteria for characterization and rank
246 assignment in this manuscript are a reflection of the current state of knowledge and
247 methodological feasibility. Future periodic evaluations should be undertaken for addition,
248 removal, or modification of the proposed criteria to account for newer observations as well as
249 experimental and bioinformatic advances.

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259 **Conflicts of Interest.** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

260 **Table 1. Proposed reporting criteria for characterization of new Neocallimastigomycota taxa.**
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Parameter	Information to provide
Morphology/Microscopic criteria¹	
Colony morphology*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of shape, size, color, and edge-center differences.
Liquid growth patterns*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of growth: thin/heavy biofilm, powdery/sand-like, cottony, ball or floc-like, attachment to the container's glass surface, color.
Zoospores* ¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zoospore flagellation pattern: monoflagellated (n=1-4); polyflagellated (n>4) • Zoospore size • Length of flagella
Thallus development pattern*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nature of thallus development: monocentric or polycentric
Sporangial development* ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nature of sporangial development: endogenous, pseudo-intercalary endogenous, and/or exogenous in monocentric taxa; terminal and/or intercalary in polycentric taxa.
Sporangiophores* ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of sporangiophore dimensions (length, width), branching (branched, unbranched), shape (eggcup shape, wide-flattened), and size (wide, narrow). • Documenting the occurrence of subsporangial swelling.
Sporangia*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of sporangial shapes (e.g., globose, ellipsoidal with or without constriction at the middle, ovoid, bowling pin-shaped, egg-shaped, pyriform, heart-shaped, triangular, mucronate with a pointed apex, elongated, rhomboidal), size, and arrangement. • Documenting sporangia uniformity or pleomorphy, and differences between various types of sporangia (e.g. exogenous versus endogenous versus intercalary). • Description of sporangial necks (the point between sporangia and sporangiophore or sporangia and rhizoid) (e.g., tightly constricted, broad), and neck ports (narrow or wide). • Documenting the occurrence of specific structures, e.g. papillae.
Zoospore release mechanism ⁺	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documenting how zoospores are released (through an apical pore, through rupture of the sporangial wall, or a combination of both). • Documenting whether sporangia dissolve, detach, and/or remain intact after spore release.
Rhizoidal growth pattern*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documenting whether fungal rhizoids are filamentous or bulbous. • For filamentous growth: Documenting the occurrence of narrow and wide hyphae, the level of branching and twisting, constriction patterns (regular or irregular intervals), and presence of rhizoidal swellings. • For bulbous hyphae, documenting the holdfast patterns (single, multiple), number of

	sporangiophore per holdfast, and number of sporangia.
Additional structures ⁺	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documenting the formation of additional specific structures during the life cycle, e.g. hyphal coils, resting stages (particularly in old cultures).
Stability of key traits ⁺³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examining cultures grown under different conditions, substrates, as well as during different stages of growth to examine trait consistency and association with various growth stages or culturing conditions.
Spore ultrastructure ⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documenting zoospores ultrastructure.
Phylogenetic criteria	
Internal transcribed spaced-1 (ITS1)* ⁴	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sequences from a minimum of 12 clones are required. Alternatively, sequences from 12 distinct copies corresponding to the amplified fragment from a sequenced genome could be utilized. • Documenting within strain variability, and phylogenetic position and relation to currently described taxa.
D1/D2 variable region of the large ribosomal subunit (D1/D2 LSU)* ⁵	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sequences from a minimum of 12 clones are required. Alternatively, sequences from 12 distinct copies corresponding to the amplified fragment from a sequenced genome could be utilized. • Documenting within strain variability, and phylogenetic position and relation to currently described taxa.
Ribosomal RNA operon ^{+6,7}	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A region covering ITS1-5.8S rRNA-ITS2-D1/D2 LSU
Additional criteria	
Substrate utilization pattern ⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documenting growth on a wide range of sugar monomers, dimers, oligomers, and plant polysaccharides (e.g. starch, cellulose, xylan, pectin/polygalacturonic acid). • Documenting growth on proteins, complex media, and/or fatty acids.
Oxygen sensitivity ⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documenting viability after challenging with atmospheric air for various time intervals (e.g. 0.5, 1, 3, 12 h or 1d)
Fermentation end products ⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documenting the production of volatile fatty acids, dicarboxylic acids, alcohol, H₂, CO₂, and other fermentation products produced with growth. • Variation in products nature/ratio when grown on different substrates.
Biogeography and ecological distribution ⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Homology search could help identify where closely related species were encountered in previous culture-independent surveys, whether the new isolates represent any of the yet-uncultured lineages, as well as possible host preferences and biogeographic patterns.

262 * Criteria indispensable for accurate assessment

263 ⁺ Criteria recommended for complete description of new Neocallimastigomycota isolates.

264 ⁰ Criteria reported in prior taxa description manuscripts, helpful for providing a complete description of new Neocallimastigomycota
265 isolates.
266

267 ¹. Determining the number of flagella on some spores could be challenging, with visualization angles and aggregation of multiple
268 flagella in a single locomotory organelle during swimming leading to uncertain counts. Observing and counting flagella from multiple
269 (e.g. > 50 zoospores) is recommended when possible, as well as reporting average numbers for polyflagellated taxa, and frequency of
270 oligo (bi-, tri-, and tetra-) flagellation in “mono”flagellated taxa.

271 ². Sporangia and sporangiophore pleomorphy has been observed in multiple genera (e.g. in genera *Feramyces* [7], and
272 *Liebetanzomyces* [39]), and could be more pronounced when different media compositions are utilized (e.g. Figure S1 in [20]). This
273 could be avoided by the utilization of standard media (e.g. cellobiose-based media utilized in [40]). Further, the level of pleomorphy in
274 itself should be reported and could be used as an informative trait for taxa delineation.

275 ³. Continuous subculturing and “domestication” of isolates could lead to changes in an isolate’s microscopic features. For example,
276 polycentric taxa often cease to produce sporangia or zoospores with continuous subculturing [41], and hence microscopic
277 characterization of such taxa should be undertaken promptly post isolation.

278 ⁴ Recommended primers to use: for the ITS1 region only, primers MN100 (TCCTACCCTTTGTGAATTTG) and MNGM2
279 (CTGCGTTCTTCATCGTTGCG) [42]. In case of possible mismatches, as observed previously [4], amplifying longer regions and
280 bioinformatically extracting the ITS1 region can also be achieved using primers Neo 18S For (AATCCTTCGGATTGGCT) and Neo
281 5.8S Rev (CGAGAACCAAGAGATCCA) for amplifying partial 18S rRNA gene, full ITS1 region and partial 5.8S rRNA gene [43],
282 or ITS1F (TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG) and ITS4R (TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC) for amplifying the whole ITS region
283 encompassing ITS1-5.8S rRNA-ITS2 [44].

284 ⁵ Recommended primers to use for amplifying the D1/D2 domains within the LSU rRNA are the general fungal primers NL1F
285 (GCATATCAATAAGCGGAGGAAAAG) and NL4R (GGTCCGTGTTTCAAGACGG) [45], or pairing the general fungal forward
286 primer NL1F with the anaerobic fungal-specific reverse primer GGNL4 (TCAACATCCTAAGCGTAGGTA) [46].

287 ⁶ Recommended primers to use are ITS1F-NL4R [29, 47].

288 ⁷ Cloning and sequencing the entire operon and bioinformatically extracting ITS1 and LSU region for phylogenetic analysis could be a
289 substitute for individual ITS1 and LSU amplification and sequencing described above. The same minimum number of clones (12)
290 recommended for individual ITS1 and D1/D2 LSU amplicons should be observed.
291

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